

Issues of Vocational and Technical Education

On Vision 20 2020

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Abstract: *Nigeria is Oil-rich but has been limped by political instability, corruption, insecurity, inadequate infrastructure, and poor macroeconomic management. Leaders have failed to diversify the economy away from its overdependence on the capital-intensive oil sector, which provides 95% of foreign exchange earnings and about 80% of budgetary revenues. Unemployment rate was 4.6% (2007est.). In 2009, of the total number of qualified secondary school students for enrollment into Universities and Polytechnics only 28% of them could be admitted, there is not enough vocational institutions that can handle the remaining 72%. The drop out figure from the educational system is put at over 30 Million, and the unemployed rate was 19.7 per cent with 52% of this unemployable i.e. have no specific skills. These indices do not support the country's vision 20, 2020 if the citizens are not educated inline with global practices. Unfortunately, massive retrenchments in the formal sector of the economy keep rising. The 6-3-3-4 education system was developed for the vocationalization of the secondary school curriculum in Nigeria. Nigeria has more than 250 vocational/technical institutions offering various technical programmes but the number of teachers is inadequate, electricity is epileptic, there is low morale. The society lacks skilled technicians: bricklayers, carpenters, and auto-mechanics, laboratory and pharmacy technicians, electrical/electronic technicians etc. Vision 20, 2020 is scary; the government must aggressively train the youths in vocational and technical education so that the country will be more secured than it is now.*

Keywords: Vision 20 2020, Corruption, Unemployment, Vocational Education, Security.

1.0 Introduction

A productive, competent, and flexible workforce is a prerequisite for furthering economic development. The demand for skilled workers and technicians is already acute and will become ever more intense as the industrial sector becomes the dominant provider of employment; yet the Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) sub-sector is unable to respond to the changing labor market requirements because of its present supply-driven orientation. Its curricula, instructional equipment, teaching methods, and evaluation techniques are outdated, leading to inappropriately low internal and external efficiencies. The management

capacity of the Technology and Science Department (TSD) is inadequate to improve the low-performing vocational and technical schools. Without intervention, the mismatch between school graduates and employer requirements will continue, and private sector-led economic growth, as espoused in the country's National Economic Empowerment Development Strategy (NEEDS) will be compromised. The mismatch is due to vocational and technical education teaching outdated skills, with outdated curriculum, machinery and equipment and the lack of consultation with and the involvement of the private sector in VTE. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2005),

Historically according to Wodi and Dokubo (2012), training in specific skills was pivotal in the development of great nations. In the United States of America, the pivotal role of vocational/technical education in her economic growth is immeasurable. Gutek (1983) maintain that as early as 1917, a federal law (Smith-Hughes Act) was passed to provide funding for vocational/technical education in response to the increasing demand by industries for technical skills. Vocational education received additional funding in the US throughout the last century. Vocational and technical schools were federally funded because as McKenzie (1983) in Wodi and Dokubo (2012) observed, the U.S business sector and industries persistently complained of the lack of synergy between the general skills thought in schools and the required specific skills for employment. Majasan (1998) observed that after independence in 1945, S. Korea re-organized its school curriculum and emphasized science and technical education. The combination of aggressive educational policies, visionary leadership and disciplined labor force revolutionized S. Korea and propelled her to economic greatness. Other nations such as Europe, Japan, China, and India made their scientific, technological, and commercial breakthrough, through the provision of sound qualitative, functional and standard education to her citizenry.

In 2008 however, the country began pursuing economic reforms. Nigeria's former military rulers failed to diversify the economy away from its overdependence on the capital-intensive oil sector, which provides 95% of foreign exchange earnings and about 80% of budgetary revenues. Oil-rich Nigeria has been limped by political instability, corruption, inadequate infrastructure, and poor macroeconomic management. UNESCO (2010) gave Nigeria gross domestic product (GDP) per capita at purchasing power parity (PPP) as \$2,500

(2010 est.) and compared 177 with the world. Agriculture, industry and service contributed 30%, 32% and 38% (2010 est.) respectively. The unemployment rate was 4.9% (2007 est.) while the population below poverty line was 70% (2007 est.) placing the country in the 45th position when compared with the rest of the world. These indices are not enough to lurch the country in the 20th position by year 2020 if the citizens are not given the right education in line with global practices. About 55.9% (male 44,296,228/female 42,534,542) of the population are in the age bracket 15-64 years- 2011 est.

According to Gerald (2010), vision 20:2020 will be a mirage if we do not zero in on educating the over one hundred and fifty million Nigerians on the importance and usage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Gerald lamented the attitude of parents on vocational studies, stressing that most parents love the aesthetics of furniture and joinery but will not encourage their children who have flair for it. He disclosed that, when Galaxy went to South Africa for a programme, he discovered that there was only one graduate amongst South African crew yet they are however sound in Information Technology. On the order hand, he said that all the crew members from Nigeria were Master Degree holders except one who has first degree.

2.0 Literature Review

Moustafa (2010), reacting to an article by Ugwuja (2010) on "Vocational Technical Education and Development" says that Technical Education (TE) educators hardly differentiate between the terms Vocational and Technical Education. The society has been led to believe that Vocational Education is for those who are incapable of pursuing technical academic programmes. Vocational education refers to skill-based programmes designed for

lower level of skills education and focuses on a specific vocation for workplace entry. It is designed to increase the general skills of the vocational trainees as part of preparatory and for secondary education system, especially in relation to their present or future occupations. Technical education, on the other hand, facilitates the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic technical and scientific knowledge in general fields. The major difference between the two terms is that, whereas vocational education is designed for a particular vocation, technical education does not target any particular vocation but gives general technical knowledge.

Bello et al (2007) say that youths represent the future and hope of every country. The high returns on resources invested in youths today have both immediate and long term benefits. Youth programmes by Seiders (1985), play an important role in building life skills of individual young people, strengthening families and communities, and working towards sustainable development as a major contributor to the overall progress of a country. Many countries have realized that developing and harnessing the potential of the youths can best be achieved through a sound educational system. According to the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004), the aim of secondary school is to make a person to be productive to himself and the society. In Nigeria, the training given to youths at the secondary school level is both pre-vocational and academic. Academic and vocational courses are offered at the Junior Secondary School (JSS) level. These courses are supposed to provide definite purpose and meaning to education by relating to occupational goals, provide technical knowledge and

work skills necessary for employment, and develop abilities, attitudes, work habits and appreciation which contributes to a satisfying and productive life.

UNESCO (2010), gives the guiding principle of education in Nigeria as the equipping of every citizen with such knowledge, skill, attitude and values as to enable him/her to derive maximum benefits from his/her membership in society, lead a fulfilling life and contribute to the development and welfare of the community. Are we doing any justice to this objective? Egwu (2009), observed that in some years past, Nigeria educational system was ranked among the best in the world. Unfortunately, there has been a drastic erosion of the quality of our educational system. The lack of instructional aid has reduced our educational system into industries producing brains alien to their society.

Omolewa (2001), contemporary issues in Nigerian education has several times been argued that the Nigeria education system is at the cross-road, and at the verge of being collapsed. From the dawn of history of education in Nigeria communities, mission agencies, individuals and other accredited bodies participated and still take some part in the provision, supervision and management of education in Nigeria. Education before government's intervention was adjudged to be of high standard. The national government took over the control of all schools after the civil war without considering the consequences of funding, provision of learning facilities, infrastructure and control of the increased population of the new entrants into these so called government institutions. Events of time past in Nigeria proved that, the total

control as assumed by the federal government led to further instability in the standard of education and a near total collapse due to political intervention in the management of education in Nigeria.

Popoola (2004) conducted a study in Oyo to evaluate the success of the implementation of the objectives of vocational/technical education at junior secondary education level buttressed this view. The study revealed that the objectives had not been achieved because of the limiting factors mentioned above as well as unstable power supply. Popoola considered a critical factor militating against the functionality of vocational/technical education in Oyo. This explains the success of VTE system in America that initiated it, and in Japan that adopted it after World War II in 1945. Vocational Technical Education succeeded in these countries because they had functional infrastructure that sustained the system; Nigeria operated the 6-3-3-4 system, but failed to copy the honesty, disciplined work force, and work ethics of these countries that made their educational system and other infrastructure function. The system is wobbling in Nigeria not because of inherent weaknesses in the system, but because we lack the requisite structures to support it. In fact, in developed economies like the U.S, market and labor demands dictate the location and curricula of vocational/technical schools, suggesting that businesses and industries that will absorb the graduates from these schools must be in place before vocational technical education can really thrive. Government should also provide incentives in the form of scholarships and grants that will attract students to embrace vocational/technical education.

2.1 Efforts at Vocationalizing Education in Nigeria

Ajakaiye (1991) in Suobere (2008) states that training for industrial occupations in vocational/technical schools are comparatively a recent phenomenon. Until the 19th Century, apprenticeships and informal training developed skills for most manual occupations, largely through association with a master usually for many years. In recent times, technological advances, analytical and communication skills were required in vocational education and training, as well as more theoretical knowledge. Uyanya (1989) stated that, the most important thing that ever happened to Nigeria is the 1981 National Policy on Education, which emphasizes the acquisition of vocational skill and self-reliance. Although, the type of education Nigerian sought and acquired served the immediate practical needs of job placement in the colonial government, it was not forward looking for the technological needs of the country. The importance of science as a necessary tool for technological development soon became imminent. Consequently, in the 1970s, the teaching of science began to assume significance in the curricula of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Integrated science came into the programmes of primary and junior classes in secondary schools. Colleges of technology and polytechnics were established and more attention was focused on university of technology. These efforts were directed towards striking a balance between tertiary and science/technical-oriented programmes for vocational education in Nigeria. The Nigerian Government took a giant step to promote the concept of vocationalism by stating among the objectives of VTE in her National Policy on Education (Revised, 1981 and 2004) as: (i) to provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development and (ii) to give training and impart the necessary skills leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians and other skilled

personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant.

These objectives were stated decades ago to redeem the bias against VTE. To this day, even though more vocational-technical institutions have been established across the nation as compared with the fewer numbers of institutions in 1981, the initial bias against, and the disdain for VTE is still evident. One fact that has remained undisputable is that Nigeria historically has a very popular and powerful aspiration towards qualifications which are now being acquired either through Full-time or Part time mode. What is surprising however is the increasing attractiveness of qualification in the face of massive retrenchments in the formal sector of the economy and massive unemployment of the 'qualified'. As early as the 1980s technical and vocational education had been made an integral aspect of general education. The 6-3-3-4 education system saw to the vocationalization of the secondary school curriculum in Nigeria. Kenya and Cameroon have even gone further to include vocational subjects at the primary level. The 6-3-3-4 system provided for pre-vocational and vocational curricular offered at the junior and senior secondary schools respectively. For the first time in the history of education in Nigeria, VTE subjects were, as a matter of national policy, to be offered side-by-side, and hopefully, enjoy parity in esteem with the 'more academic' courses hitherto run by the secondary grammar schools under the old colonial-based system of education. To this end, the national curriculum on Agriculture, Introductory Technology, Home Economics, Business Studies (Junior Secondary School Level), Agricultural Science, Clothing and Textile, Home Management, Food and Nutrition, Typewriting & Shorthand, Principles of Accounts, Commerce, Woodwork, Technical Drawing, Basic Electronics, and Auto-Mechanics came into being in

Nigerian secondary schools. As one of the innovations that should distinguish the products of the new system from the old, school work was now based on these curricula in both private and public schools from 1982 through government's directive that post-primary schools should be more comprehensive a policy already reflected in the National Policy on Education had earlier proposed in 1981.

To Wodi and Dokubo (2012), vocational/technical education neither thrived in 6-3-3-4 system nor in Colleges of Education (Technical). Since the incidence of school drop-out at secondary level is not abetting, creative ways of generating interest in vocational/technical education must be crafted. It is rather paradoxical that the same youths who despise vocational/technical education, learn the same skills through apprenticeship and often demonstrate mastery of the skill. High enrolment in computer training centers, and electronic repair workshops, which usually lasts for a few months, suggests that vocational/technical education among Nigerian youths will thrive if other supportive structures are in place. It may be difficult for any nation to develop without the contribution of vocational and technical education.

2.2 Problems facing VTE in the Country

Vocation and Technical education play a unique role in a country's technological growth and development. Unfortunately, their impact has scarcely been felt because it has been observed that most of the technical institutions have not discharged their duties well to influence the lives of the youths to equip them with skills, necessary for effective employment in their chosen career. Many of these institutions are currently having problems in striking a good balance between the

theory and practice of their trades, thus creating a vacuum for supply of trained and skilled Technical manpower for most industries, private entrepreneur and even the government who focus on them for such supply and instead have continued to import skills to perform the most routine jobs.

To Oni (2006) staffing and finance are major problems facing VTE. Currently, there are staffing problems. As in science, vocational-technical teachers are few compared to teachers in traditional secondary schools. In the past, the Nigerian government gave financial incentives to science teachers to encourage students to study science and to retain those already in the profession. Today, these teachers no longer receive such allowances and where they do receive them they are irregularly paid because of the current socioeconomic crisis in the country. Majority of the teachers are also discouraged and disillusioned because of the inability of government to provide science laboratories and corresponding equipment in the institutions. Certainly, VTE is expensive to run because it requires large amount of money to build workshops, classrooms and to maintain competent staff as well as provide adequate equipment and facilities. Currently, Nigeria has more than 250 vocational/technical institutions offering various technical programmes across the country.

Stella (2011), on Education sector under democracy opined that Nigeria has witnessed a steady decline in the fortune of the education sector, going from the era of military rule to the present democratic dispensation which took off in 1999. Leadership Sunday investigation reveal that the budget pattern steadily fell in value from 1999 to date, raising concerns that the country may not meet the 2015 target of "Education For All" (EFA). It was also gathered that, when compared to

the annual budget, the percentage budgeted for the education sector is much at variance with the UNESCO benchmark of 26 per cent. This can be observed in table3 in the appendix.

To Ogidefa (2010), materials and facilities needed to develop technologically are grossly inadequate for the students' population, most are outdated or stolen, and funds are not made available to procure the required instructional materials, equipment and provision of the necessary facilities. According to Babalola (1991) vocational education equipment are allowed to deteriorate because spare parts are hard to find, probably due to the cost of maintenance which may exceed the potential benefits. Basic materials are often in short supply, and overhead funds are lacking or not released to time.

There is also general apathy towards the programme. A general thinking by the public and students alike is that VTE is meant for dull and academically never-do-well students. Graduates of VTE are discriminated against. This discrimination is virtually visible amongst graduates of technical schools (technical college, monotechnics, colleges of technologies, polytechnics) and those from the universities. Quality Teachers are few/inadequate no nation can rise above the quality of her teachers, the chief propagator of any form of education. To Asoluka and Okezie (2011), the fundamental factor that accounts for the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria includes the: (i) Poor Economic Growth Rate, (ii) Adoption of Untimely Economic Policy Measures, (iii) Neglect of the Agricultural Sector, (iv) Poor Enabling Environment and (v) Wrong Impression About Technical And Vocational Studies.

To John and Bright (2011), one of the greatest challenges facing the Nigeria economy is unemployment which has maintained a rising trend over the years.

The total labor force in Nigeria is made up of all persons aged 15-64 years excluding students, home keepers, retired persons and stay-at-home to work or not interested. Unemployed refers to people who are willing and are capable of work but are unable to find suitable paid employment.

2.3 Consequences of Neglect of VTE

Victor (2009) opined that while VTE has continued to thrive in many societies, Nigeria has neglected this aspect of education. Consequently, the society lacks skilled technicians: bricklayers, carpenters, painters and auto mechanics, laboratory and pharmacy technicians, electrical/electronic technicians and skilled vocational nurses, etc. The hospitals are no longer a place where people go to get their ailments treated, but a place they go and die. Tales abound of how people die during surgeries and out of minor ailments. The half-baked roadside mechanics in the society cause more harm to vehicles when contracted to service vehicles, and because of poor training some of the commercial drivers have sent many people to their early death. The shabby performance of Nigeria's house builders (mason/bricklayers, etc.) is no longer news. Kingsley(2010)attributes the rising incidents of building collapse to the use of substandard building materials and incompetent professionals in construction activities. Individuals with important projects now use competent technicians from neighboring countries. This is not to mention the havoc the poorly trained technicians have caused in the power sector. Nigeria's epileptic electricity supply is the greatest bottleneck to national development. Many to-be technicians have lost enthusiasm to continue training and instead have resulted to "Ocada" business for lack of power to run practical or their businesses. Nigerians toiling all day in the field with knives, hoes, and shovels would not feed the nation's over 170 million people.

Mechanized farming requires technical skills that could be obtained in technical and vocational schools. Every facet of the economy has been affected by lack of skilled technicians. The financial sector lacks technicians to regulate the banks and to develop financial software to properly tackle the rising fraudulent activities in the banking sector. Without security development is impossible in a society; no nation can sustain its democracy if the citizens lack confidence in the police. The police violate the citizens' human and civil rights and lack forensic laboratory and fingerprint technicians to conduct criminal investigations. The certificated "professionals" cannot find jobs, they roam the streets and have resulted to destructive alternatives like kidnappings and bomb blasting. The lack of tools to track down criminals has led to rising cases of bomb blasts all over the country. The whole of the northern states have experienced one form of bomb blast or the other. The eastern part of the country has being distressed with kidnappings. The danger posed by environmental pollution and fake drugs is alarming; the society lacks the skill to manage HIV and AIDS, cancer and diabetes among other serious health problems. The country however prides her-self in propagandas on prevention rather than on invention.

The neglect of technical education is socially and economically injurious because it is robbing the nation of the contributions the graduates would make on national development. Most of the so-called "expatriate engineers" who are being paid millions of dollars to build Nigeria roads and bridges are graduates of technical and vocational colleges, yet the Nigerian leaders do not see any reason to take technical institutions seriously.

3.0 Methods and Materials

Secondary data on unemployment rate were collected from National bureau of Statistics NBS (2010), and the Central Bank Reports covering the periods between 2002 and 2012 while the percent of Nigeria budgetary allocation to the education sector were collected from Civil Society Action Coalition on Education for All (SCACEFA). Some examples of vocational activities presented were obtained from different web sources. The method adopted here is a descriptive one. We investigated the ability of the educational system to cater for the training needs of the country. We identified some types of vocational opportunities available to people. We investigated the rate of unemployment in the country within the study period. The possible relationship between budgetary allocation to education and the rate of unemployment in the country was also investigated. For the analysis, the geometric average of percent rate of unemployment for all states were obtained and graphs drawn. Pictures were also used where applicable.

4.0 Results and Discussions

To Oseni (1012), Despite Nigeria's abundant mineral resources, demographic figures put Nigeria as very poor because of underdeveloped human and natural resources: the estimated population is about 167 Million, the annual birth rate is about 6 Million, the GDP per Capita is \$2000, out of the total number of children who must undergo basic and compulsory education (6-14 years), 10% of eligible children are unable to go to school, the success rate of primary school final grade is 75%, of the 75% eligible for secondary school education, only 30% can be enrolled leaving 70% drop out. To him,

132 accredited technical colleges and 70 vocational enterprises centers have dilapidated and obsolete facilities. Of about 100 Nigeria's accredited Polytechnics and 164 Monotechnics, only 22% of total applicants in 2009 could be admitted, and only 3% was admitted in 2010. Of the total number of qualified secondary school students for enrollment into universities and polytechnics only 28% of them could be "admitted" and there are not enough vocational institutions that can handle the remaining 72%. The aggregate drop out of the educational system is put at over 30 Million, and the unemployment figures put at 49 Million with 52% of this unemployable i.e. have no specific skills.

From Graph 1, it could be observed that the rate of unemployment throughout the country was volatile over the period. From table 2 and graph 1, it could be observed from the second and third columns of table 2, Niger state had the least unemployment rate of 0.2% in year 2005, the state had its maximum of 39.4% in 2011. Zamfara state had its minimum of 12.8% in 2007, and its maximum of 71.5% in 2003, the highest over the period. With this analysis, Zamfara state has had majority of its able-bodied youth without job for most of the period under study. Graph 1 is divided into two sections: states in section "A" have their minimum unemployment rate between 0.2% for Niger state and 4.8% for Benue state and their maximum unemployment rate between 13.6% for Osun state and 67% for Benue state. States in section "B" have their minimum unemployment rate between 5.30% for the Federal Capital territory (FCT) and 12.80% for Zamfara state which happens to be the worst of all the states in this regard.

The maximum unemployment rate for section "B" was between 15.50% for Abia state and 71.50% for Zamfarastate. From Table 4, Nigeria compared with 199 countries of the world with an unemployment rate of 21% in 2011 was in the 162nd position. Monaco was in the first position with 0% unemployment rate, CIA (2012). Ghana which has similar history with Nigeria had an unemployment rate of 11% (CIA 2011est). If Ghana's case is used as a benchmark for Nigeria's rate, and using the average measure in column 4 table 2 as our guide, Ghana outperformed Nigeria by 67.66% (25 out of 37states).

Graph 2 shows a possible relationship between percentages of Federal Budget allocated to the Education sector between year 1995 and year 2012 and the average unemployment rate for the country between years 2002 and 2012. The last row of Table 1 contains the geometric average of unemployment rates of the states in Nigeria in the study period. From Graph 2, the tendency is that as budgetary allocation increases, average unemployment rate decreases especially between years 2007 and 2012. Picture 1 shows Technicians undergoing training in a Technical college. Trainees are exposed to different types of machines in the process of production. Picture 2 shows molding business where youths can be exposed to Pottery and Ceramic productions. Picture 3 shows laboratory technicians in a dispensary unit of the pharmacy of a hospital. Picture 4 shows automobile technician in a training section. These are few from so many types of vocations with obviously heavy and costly equipment. Pictures 5 to picture 8 show some of the consequences of poor and ill-equipped training of the youths. Pictures 5

and 7 show direct effect of ill-maintained vehicles and bad roads a common feature of Nigerian roads. Most mechanics are not well trained they cause more damages to vehicles contracted to them for repairs. The technicians who construct our roads are not well trained or are corrupt and only use fraction of total contract sum for the execution of road construction awarded to them. While Picture 8 shows collapsed high buildings in Lagos, Picture 6 shows properties damaged through bombing by the Boko Haram sects in Nigeria. This is one of the resultant effects of unemployment of abled-bodied youths of the country. These youths are easily lured into bombings, kidnappings, bank robberies to mention a few. An idle hand is the devils workshop goes an adage. All these are in line with views of Victor (2009).

5.0 Recommendations

To Aladekomo (2004), the challenges of technical and vocational education and training in Nigeria are many. The first is that there is need to reorient VTE more towards self-employment by the active teaching of enterprise education in every technical and vocational school/college. In Nigeria technical degrees are regarded as inferior to regular academic degrees this is not good enough, the worth of every worker should depend on what value is the person going to add to the economy, and not on the stack of academic degrees. McGrath (1998a) observed that in preparing VTE graduates for sustainable self-employment, enterprise education should be collaborated with post training support factors, e.g. capital, equipment, contracts etc. This will foster the success of the new idea of 'Technopreneur' which is already gaining ground in East and South Africa. Ogidefa (2010), nations that

are developed are the ones that have cemented relationship with VTE. This is what differentiates the developed nations and developing nations. Aina (2005) in Ogidefanoted that great nations of the world: USA, Europe, Japan, China, and India made their scientific, technological, and commercial breakthrough, through the provision of sound qualitative, functional and standard education to her citizenry. To achieve this lofty goal, the government must be ready and willing to develop technical education. The current move to teach entrepreneurial courses in schools should be made sustainable.

Nigeria's current preoccupation with university education reduces economic opportunities of those who are more oriented toward work than academe. Not everyone needs a university education. Awarding licenses to greedy organizations and individuals to establish private universities that are not even as equipped as some of the technical and vocational schools cannot develop the society. Because of the sorry state of the nation's tertiary institutions many of the graduates lack "employability" skills, which would easily be acquired from technical and vocational colleges. It is no longer news that the nation's youth unemployment rate has been shooting up the sky and the poor quality of graduates worrisome. There should be some form of school-work-based learning incorporated in schools in Nigeria as integral part of national development strategy. Empowering the people with technical skills would enhance their productivity and national development.

To Kingsley (2010), only professionals must be involved in building contracts and must be men of knowledge and integrity. They should be motivated towards providing the best professional service at reasonable price and in a timely manner. The professional regulatory organs and

their corresponding societies or associations should conduct mandatory regular workshops or seminars for their members to keep them abreast of current developments in their chosen profession. The nation's technical schools should be upgraded to international standards by employing quality teachers with field and academic experience in their subject areas. Only experienced and professional administrators should be appointed to run technical institutions. Technical graduates should be thoroughly certified before they could work as technicians as it is obtained in the developed nations.

The turn out from secondary and post-secondary institutions are on the increase, more vocational centers should be established with well-equipped laboratory and workshops to teach these candidates vocational skills that will make them job providers rather than jobs seekers. The energy sector should be fixed to generate enough electricity for small scale and medium scale industries. Alternative sources of energy should be explored. Fix the roads and bridges for easy transportation of man and materials.

The leaders of Nigeria must salvage her image first by re-branding the mentality of the people through the tackling of corruption, reform the electoral system and fix the dilapidated institutions. Without a fundamental shift in values, beliefs and thinking, and without technological capability, Nigeria will continue to dream of becoming a 'Great Nation.' To Aladekomo (2004), the gap between the Nigeria Entrepreneur and the university and the polytechnics should be bridged. Very few entrepreneurs have meaningful interaction with the Universities and Polytechnics. He is of the opinion that i) establishments should allow academics to spend some time with them especially during their sabbatical leave ii) they should allow some of their staff do in-

service training in tertiary institution iii) they should share their experiences with students and staff when invited for workshops/seminars etc iv) the establishments should finance/sponsor special research related to their businesses. The author further suggests that: Entrepreneurship development should be made part and parcel of tertiary Institutions' curriculum. All institutions should teach a course in entrepreneurship, the coverage and complexity of which will vary with the level of the institution. There is need for a change in the mind-set of the youths to see self-employment as an alternative to white collar jobs before leaving school and be prepared psychologically and emotionally for it. Vocational-technical educators should be encouraged to organize workshops, seminars and conferences in primary and secondary schools on the value and the relevance of vocational education to individual and national development.

Employers and governments at the state and federal levels should encourage on-the-job- training of workers in public and private sectors. Attachment of middle level technicians to businesses and industries for upgrading of skills can help diversify vocational technical training at minimal costs to government. Also, individual efforts in technological production should be encouraged. This is in line with the opinion of Oni (2006). The country's apathy towards her innovators must change. Where is late Professor Awojobi's *Autonov 1*? How about Dr. Jeremiah Abalaka innovation? Of recent Professor Isaiah Ibeh, the Dean of the School of Basic Medical Science of the University of Benin claimed to have discovered an herbal drug to cure HIV/AIDS. Instead of Nigerians encouraging these people, Nigerians will start a media war to put those ideas in the dustbins. Nigerians can spend billions of naira to sponsor sports but cannot spend millions of naira to encamp initiators of

discoveries if only to set target for them to come out with internationally accepted results. Government at all levels should provide adequate financial support to polytechnics and technical colleges to effectively manage their academic programmes, maintain facilities and provide benefits and adequate incentives for their workers. Federal government budgetary allocation to the education sector must be improved to meet the UNESCO 26% benchmark. The moderating agencies should ensure that qualified and competent teachers are employed to teach pre-vocational and vocational courses as recommended in our National Policy on Education. The federal government needs to encourage young potentials who are contributing their impact technologically to develop our society and give them incentives for their talents. The right curriculum that will produce the right labor should be designed and implemented. The federal government should as a matter of urgency endeavor to provide modern training facilities, equipment, machinery and instructional materials in all levels of technical education. The local, state and federal government should increase the funding into the nation's VTE sector. Government should encourage the training of good quality VTE teachers. Encourage in-service training, attendance at workshops/conferences and seminars. There should be a workable collaboration between VTE institutions and functional organization having up-to-date or modern facilities materials and equipment/machinery for sound training of students. These are in line with Ogidefa (2010).

To Wodi and Dokubo op cit, the educational sector, is a subsystem being influenced by other sectors (such as energy, financial institutions, politics, and other socioeconomic factors), which constitute other subsystems. When these other sectors (subsystems) are

dysfunctional, then the educational system cannot function in isolation. For instance, it is impossible for vocational/technical education to be strong in the absence of stable power supply to operate the machines. Nor can it thrive where technical/vocational subjects are taught theoretically like in history, for lack of fund to procure necessary equipment, construct workshops, and employ trained teachers.

6.0 Conclusion

It cannot be overemphasized that VTE is the engine for economic growth. No nation can fight a war without an army. Nigeria cannot develop without well-equipped vocational and technical institutions. Nigerians need to create a new approach for the concept of vocational education and its purpose to the society. Vocational education is not specifically meant for the mentally retarded, physically handicapped and socially maladjusted and of course dropouts from formal school system. It is a highly useful education for all because its occupational content offers the trainees the opportunity to acquire skills, attitude and knowledge which are needed for the technological growth of our nation. Nigeria should seriously invest in education and skill training as no nation can compete effectively in the emerging global market place with poorly educated and unskilled workers. The leading factors of production in the emerging global economy are said to be technology, knowledge, creativity and innovation. The Vision 20, 2020 will remain a paper tiger without VTE being a major part of the strategy.

References

Aladekomo, F. O. (2004); Nigeria Educational Policy and Entrepreneurship, Kamla-Raj Journal of Social Sciences, Vol. 9(2): 75-83

Asoluka, N. and Okezie, A. I. (2011). Unemployment and Nigerian Economic Growth (1985-2009), International Association for Teaching and Learning (IATEL), Proceedings of the 2011 International Conference on Teaching, Learning and Change. pg. 4-6

Babalola, J.B. (1991): A Comparative Analysis of Education Development in Selected African Countries. A paper presented at the World Conference on Comparative Adult Education, Ibadan, University.

Bello, M. I., Danjuma, I. M., Adamu, A. Y. (2007); A Survey of Vocational Training Needs of 15–25 Years Old Out-of-School Youths in Bauchi Metropolis, Journal of Career and Technical Education, Vol. 23, No. 1, Fall, 2007

CIA World Factbook (2012) Country Comparison of Unemployment Rate, <http://www.indexmundi.com/g/r.aspx?v=74> Accessed 01/02/2013.

Egwu, S. (2009); “Universities and the national education roadmap” being a keynote address by the Honourable Minister of Education, on the occasion of the 24th conference of the association of vice- chancellors of Nigerian universities, at the university of Ilorin.

Federal republic of Nigeria (1981). National policy on Education (Revised) Lagos NERDC press.

Federal republic of Nigeria (2004). National policy on Education (Revised) Lagos NERDC press.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2005), Skills Training And Vocational Education Project Appraisal Report, Department Of Social

- Development Centre And West Region Pg vii
- Federal Republic of Nigeria.(1998). National policy on education (Bed.). Lagos: NERDC.
- Gerald Ilukwe (2010). Nigeria Educational System in the Internet Age, a speech delivered at the 65th anniversary of Government College Ughelli Old Boys Association (GCUOBA) held at the National Arts Theatre, Lagos. <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2010/08/> Accessed 01/02/2013
- Guttek, G. (1983). Education and Schooling in America. NJ: Prentice-Hall. Pg 91
- John O. A. and Bright O. O. (2011). Poverty and youth Unemployment in Nigeria, 1987-2011, International Journal of Business and Social Science Vol. 3 No. 20 [Special Issue – October 2012]
- Kingsley, O. D. (2010). Incessant Incidents of Building Collapse in Nigeria: A Challenge to Stakeholders, Global Journal of Researches in Engineering, Vol.10 Issue 4. Pp 75-84.
- Majasan, J. (1998). Qualitative Education and Development. Ibadan: Spectrum Books pg56
- Mcgrath, S. (1998a); "From Policy to Practice: Education Training and Self Employment in Kenya" Paper Nigeria Educational Policy And Entrepreneurship Presented at the Conference held in the Centre for African studies. University of Edinburgh. 26-27th May 1998.
- McKenzie, F. (1983).The Yellow Brick Road of Education.In J. Noll (Ed.).Taking Sides: Clashing views on Controversial Educational Issues. CT: Dushkin.
- Ogidefa, I. (2010); Enhancing Technical Vocational Education in Nigerian Schools.[http://socyberity.com/education/enhancing-technical-](http://socyberity.com/education/enhancing-technical-vocational-education-in-nigerian-schools/)
- [vocalional-education-in-nigerian-schools/](http://www.vanguardngr.com/2010/08/) Accessed 2/2/2013
- Omolewa, M. (2001).*The challenge of education in Nigeria*.Ibadan: University of Ibadan Press.
- Oni C.S. (2006); Vocationalism in Nigerian Education, Journal of Social Sciences, ObafemiAwolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria,12(2): 147-150,
- Oseni, M. I. (1012) Training of Engineering Technicians And Craftsmen as A Vehicle Of Transformation, A paper presented at the 21st COREN Engineering Assembly held on 4th and 5th September , 2012 in Abuja
- Popoola, G. C. (2004). AN investigation into the Implementation of the objectives into Vocational / Technical Education in Oyo State. Published M. phil. Thesis: O A U, Ife.
- Seiders, R. W. (1985). Background Paper: FAO's role in support of rural youth programmes and possibilities for the future. Rome: FAO Development Educational Exchange papers.
- STELLA, E. (2011): Education Sector Worse Under Democracy – Investigation, Sunday LeadershipNewspaper, http://www.leadership.ng/nga/articles/4709/2011/09/education_sector_worse_under_democracy_%E2%80%93_investigation.html Accessed 28/01/2013
- Suobere T. P. (2008); Constraints to the effective implementation of vocational education program in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt local government area, apjce.org/volume_9/apjce_9_2_59_71.pdf.
- Ugwuja, S. I. (2010). Vocational technical education and developmentFurtune News February 26, 2010.www.nigeriabestforum.com/b

- [log/?p=38404](#). Accessed 23rd January 2013.
- United Nations Educational, scientific and Cultural Organization (2010); Financing Technical and Vocational Education: Modalities and Experiences prepared by UNESCO in co-operation with the Industrial Occupations Promotion Centre of the German Foundation for International Development.
- United Nations Educational, scientific and Cultural Organization (2010); World Data on Education, 7th Edition 2010/11.
- Uyanya, R. E. (1989). Teachers' motivation and work ethics. Nigerian Journal of Technical Education, 6(1), 10-15.
- Victor E. D. (2009); Addressing Youth Unemployment and Poverty In Nigeria: A Call For Action, Not Rhetoric; Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa Vol. 11, No.3.pg 136
- Victor E. D. (2009); Technical and Vocational Education: Key to Nigeria's Development Nigerian Village Square, <http://NigerianVillageSquare.com/articles/victordike/technical-and-vocational-education-key-to-nigerias-development.html> Accessed 13/12/2012
- Wodi, S. W. and Dokubo, A.(2012). Innovation & Change in Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria: Challenges for Sustainable Industrial Development British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences Vol.10 No.I, pg. 54 <http://www.bjournal.co.uk/BJASS.aspx> Accessed 17/10/2012

Appendix

Table1: Unemployment Rates by states in Nigeria 2002- 2011

State	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
Abia	14.8	11.4	9.7	7.9	13.5	10.9	14.5	14.5	15.5	11.2
Adamawa	12.9	11.9	16.7	21.4	17.9	11.9	29.4	29.4	31.4	18.4
A/Ibom	12.3	14.4	14.4	14.4	15.3	13.5	34.1	34.1	36.1	18.4
Anambra	6.6	9.1	9.5	9.8	10.8	11.1	16.8	16.8	17.8	12.2
Bauchi	10.4	20.5	25.1	29.7	23.9	7.3	37.2	37.2	39.2	41.4
Bayelsa	3.5	7.1	14	20.9	16	6.9	38.4	38.4	40.4	23.9
Benue	8.2	4.8	11.7	18.6	10.8	67.4	8.5	8.5	9.5	14.2
Borno	6.4	0.8	3.6	6.3	5.8	7.8	27.7	27.7	29.7	29.1
C/River	7.9	12	11.5	11.1	16.9	11.8	14.3	14.3	15.3	18.2
Delta	14.9	17.1	10.8	4.5	13.8	18.9	18.4	18.4	20.8	27.2
Ebonyi	2.8	16.7	11.8	7	10.9	11.5	12	12	13	23.1
Edo	4.8	3.1	6.5	9.9	8.6	5.1	12.2	12.2	13.2	35.2
Ekiti	17.5	8.2	7.9	7.5	8.7	15.6	20.6	20.6	22.6	12.1
Enugu	15.2	16.5	21.6	27.4	20	11.5	14.9	14.9	15.9	25.2

Gombe	13.4	7.6	15.2	22.8	15.6	10.5	32.1	32.1	34.1	38.7
Imo	19.9	22.1	19.3	16.5	21.5	7.6	20.8	20.8	22.8	35.9
Jigawa	6.1	20.5	19.8	19.1	21.6	17.4	26.5	26.5	28.5	35.9
Kaduna	8.4	19.6	15.9	12.1	14.1	5.9	11.6	11.6	12.6	30.3
Kano	12.8	25.9	22.5	19.1	19.4	12.7	27.6	27.6	29.6	21.3
Katsina	10.4	20.3	22.1	23.8	19.3	5.8	37.3	37.3	39.3	28.1
Kebbi	12.3	19.8	19.9	19.9	15.2	11.8	12	12	13	25.3
Kogi	19.9	14.9	11.8	8.7	12.5	16.5	19	19	21	14.4
Kwara	8.8	5.4	4.2	2.9	7.5	16.4	11	11	12	7.1
Lagos	8	25.6	16.1	6.5	15.5	10.2	19.5	19.5	20.5	8.3
Nasarawa	1.6	5.1	6.9	8.7	8.1	7.6	10.1	10.1	11.1	36.5
Niger	6.3	6.7	3.5	0.2	3.6	17	11.9	11.9	12.9	39.4
Ogun	9.2	1.3	1.9	2.5	2.3	3.9	8.5	8.5	9.5	22.9
Ondo	16.8	7.3	6.8	6.2	6.7	5.8	14.9	14.9	16.9	12.5
Osun	1	0.4	1.2	1.9	2.7	6.3	12.6	12.6	13.6	3
Oyo	7	0.8	3.1	5.3	4.3	6.5	14.9	14.9	15.9	8.9
Plateau	11.8	0.4	1.6	2.8	2.9	8.7	7.1	7.1	8.1	25.3
Rivers	6.6	15.3	11.2	7	25	4.7	27.9	27.9	29.9	25.5
Sokoto	4.1	4.9	4.5	4.1	6.4	12.1	22.4	22.4	24.4	17.9
Taraba	16.8	23.8	13.6	3.4	14	5.9	26.8	26.8	28.8	12.7
Yobe	15	12.1	10.7	8	13.6	19.9	27.3	27.3	29.3	35.6
Zamfara	46.4	71.5	61.3	51.1	50.8	12.8	13.3	13.3	14.3	42.6
FCT	14.4	5.3	5.9	6.5	16.4	16.4	21.5	21.5	23.5	21.1
Nigeria	12.6	14.8	13.4	11.9	13.7	14.6	19.7	19.7	21.5	23.9

Source: NBS (2010); CBN Annual Report and Statement of Account (various issues)

Table 2: Minimum, Maximum and Average Unemployment Rates by State in Nigeria Between 2002 – 2011

State	Min Rate	Max Rate	Ave Rate
Niger	0.20	39.40	6.48
Plateau	0.40	25.30	4.72
Osun	0.40	13.60	3.16
Borno	0.80	29.70	9.00
Oyo	0.80	15.90	6.18
Ogun	1.30	22.90	4.90
Nasarawa	1.60	36.50	8.12
Ebonyi	2.80	23.10	10.77
Kwara	2.90	16.40	7.70
Edo	3.10	35.20	8.84
Taraba	3.40	28.80	14.47
Bayelsa	3.50	40.40	16.06
Sokoto	4.10	24.40	9.55

Delta	4.50	27.20	15.11
Rivers	4.70	29.90	14.93
Benue	4.80	67.40	11.98
FCT	5.30	23.50	13.35
Katsina	5.80	39.30	21.29
Ondo	5.80	16.90	9.94
Kaduna	5.90	30.30	12.98
Jigawa	6.10	35.90	20.45
Lagos	6.50	25.60	13.62
Anambra	6.60	17.80	11.52
Bauchi	7.30	41.40	23.96
Ekiti	7.50	22.60	12.96
Gombe	7.60	38.70	19.48
Imo	7.60	35.90	19.54
C/River	7.90	18.20	13.00
Abia	7.90	15.50	12.14
Yobe	8.00	35.60	17.84
Kogi	8.70	21.00	15.26
Enugu	11.50	27.40	17.71
Kebbi	11.80	25.30	15.54
Adamawa	11.90	31.40	18.91
A/Ibom	12.30	36.10	18.91
Kano	12.70	29.60	21.02
Zamfara	12.80	71.50	30.64
Nigeria	11.90	23.90	16.12

Source: Authors Calculations from Table 1

Table 3: Federal Government % of Budgetary Allocation to Education in Nigeria, 1995 to 2012 and Average Unemployment Rate between 2002 and 2012

Year	% of Budget	UMP Rate
1995	7.20	
1996	10.2	
1997	8.59	
1998	8.20	
1999	16.8	
2000	9.83	
2001	4.08	
2002	7.89	12.60
2003	7.96	14.80
2004	10.2	13.40
2005	8.40	11.90

2006	10.2	13.70
2007	10.5	14.60
2008	10.6	19.70
2009	10.6	19.70
2010	6.20	21.50
2011	6.20	23.90
2012	8.43	16.12

Source: Civil Society Action Coalition on Education for All (SCACEFA) office, and Author's calculation from Table 1

Table 4: Country Comparison of Unemployment Rate (2011 est)

Rank	Country	UEMRate (%)
1	Zimbabwe	95
2	Nauru	90
3	Liberia	85
4	Burkina Faso	77
5	Turkmenistan	60
6	Cocos (Keeling) Islands	60
7	Djibouti	59
8	Namibia	51.2
9	Senegal	48
10	Nepal	46
11	Kosovo	45.3
12	Lesotho	45
13	Bosnia and Herzegovina	43.3
14	Haiti	40.6
15	Gaza Strip	40
16	Kenya	40
17	Swaziland	40
18	Marshall Islands	36
19	Yemen	35
20	Afghanistan	35
21	Macedonia	31.4
22	Mali	30
23	Libya	30
24	Mauritania	30
25	Cameroon	30
26	American Samoa	29.8
27	Grenada	25
28	South Africa	24.9
29	West Bank	23.5
30	Serbia	23.4
31	Dominica	23

32	Equatorial Guinea	22.3
33	Micronesia, Federated States of Micronesia	22
34	Spain	21.7
35	Gabon	21
36	Cape Verde	21
37	Nigeria	21
...
82	Ghana	11
...
197	Thailand	0.7
198	Qatar	0.4
199	Monaco	0

Source: CIA World Factbook (2012)

Graph 1: Multiple Unemployment Rates (UEMPRate) showing Minimum, Maximum and Average Rates for each State between 2002 and 2011

Source: Authors Calculations and drawing 2012

Graph 2: Multiple Graph of % Budget Allocation and Yearly Unemployment Rate 1995-2012

Source: Authors Calculations and drawing 2012

Picture 1: Training teachers & shop foremen in a Technical Education Centre in Nititingou (Benin)
Source:fivesgroup.com

Picture 2: Approaches in TVE and training
Source: the canadianencyclopedia.com

Picture 3: Pharmacy at the Evangel Hospital in Jos, Nigeria and a lab technician.
Source:globalenvision.org

Picture 4: Assisted, reaffirming government commitment to TVET.
Source: presidency.gov.gh

Picture 5: Road Traffic Accident is a common occurrence on Nigeria roads.
Source: Ngonewsafrika.org

Picture 6: One of the havocs perpetrated by Boko Haram in Nigeria.
Source: wordonfire.org

Picture 7: Nigeria is among developing countries with poor road network.
Source: ngonewssfrica.org

Picture 8: One of the collapsed high buildings in Lagos.
, Source: ngozigold.com